

SIMPLE, DESIGN-ORIENTED COMPOSITE FAILURE CRITERIA INCORPORATING SIZE EFFECTS

Carl Zweben
Advanced Technology Manager and Division Fellow
Lockheed Martin Corporation
Martin Marietta Astro Space
King of Prussia, Pennsylvania, USA 19406

ABSTRACT

The great success of composite materials is leading to their use in increasingly larger structures, such as bridges and aircraft fuselages, which may have material volumes ten orders of magnitude greater than those of standard test coupons used to establish allowable strength values employed in design. There is a significant body of evidence showing significant decreases in strength properties of composites with increasing volume. This phenomenon, well established for tensile strength of brittle materials, is known as size effect. We review data for axial tension, compression and flexure; transverse tension; the influence of hole size and number of holes on the strength of laminates; and other phenomena. We briefly consider current design practice, multiaxial failure criteria and statistical strength theories, and propose a simple, design-oriented methodology incorporating size effects.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have become standard materials in aircraft structures and sports equipment. Their great success is leading to increasing use in countless other applications, including very large structures, such as vehicular bridges. They are also being considered for very large commercial aircraft components, such as wings and fuselages. For such applications, destructive tests of full size development models, common in the past, may be physically or economically impractical. This makes reliable design methods more important. Two key issues are material strength design allowables and multiaxial failure criteria. We address both in this paper.

Strength allowables are the strength values used in the design and analysis of structural components. They are typically established using coupons whose dimensions are in the range of 2 mm thick, 20 mm wide and 200 mm long, corresponding to a volume of the order of 0.00001 m^3 . The volume of material in a large structure can easily be ten orders of magnitude greater. Considering this great difference, it is prudent to question the validity of such an extrapolation. This is particularly true in view of the fact that, as we shall see, there is a considerable body of evidence that composite strength properties, including compression strength as well as tensile strength, may decrease significantly with increasing volume. These effects have been largely ignored so far. However, in the past, the industry has relied heavily on destructive tests to verify designs. For very large structures, destructive tests may not be possible for economic or physical reasons. Consequently, reliable design methods, strength design allowables and failure criteria are likely to assume more importance in the future.

It is widely recognized that the tensile strength of ceramics depends on the volume of stressed material and the nature of the stress distribution. These effects occur because ceramic strength is flaw sensitive, and flaw severity and distribution are generally statistical in nature. As the probability of finding large flaws increases with increasing material volume, the tensile strength

of large brittle bodies tends to be lower than that of smaller ones. This is known as size effect. Weibull developed a famous and widely used statistical theory to predict the strength of flaw-sensitive materials subjected to arbitrary stress distributions [1]. As we shall see, the existence of significant size effects in composite materials has important and potentially critical implications for large structures.

In this paper, we concentrate on polymer matrix composites (PMCs), which are the leading composites of interest for large structures at the present time. We believe that many of the ideas discussed here also apply to ceramic matrix, carbon/carbon and metal matrix composites.

The key inorganic fibers used in PMCs, such as glasses, carbons and boron, are all brittle materials. Aramid fibers, the leading organic reinforcements, are not truly brittle, but like ceramics they have relatively linear tensile stress-strain curves, and their tensile strengths are flaw sensitive. The most widely used structural PMC matrices, epoxies, polyesters, bismaleimides and polyimides, are also rather brittle materials. In short, PMCs consist of inherently brittle, flaw sensitive matrices reinforced with inherently brittle, flaw sensitive fibers. The manufacturing processes used to make composites also are a source of defects in structures.

In view of the lack of ductility of their constituents, it should not be surprising that virtually all the key composites have more or less linear tensile stress-strain curves when subjected to axial and transverse tensile stresses and strengths which display significantly more scatter than those of ductile metals. In addition, composite failure is typically catastrophic, although composite failure processes are complex, so that failure surfaces are much more irregular than those of monolithic ceramics. Considering that PMC reinforcements and matrices are brittle materials which independently display tensile strength size effects, it is logical to inquire whether the axial and transverse tensile strengths of composites made from them also have size effects.

PMCs loaded in axial compression also have relatively linear stress-strain curves and fail catastrophically, with the exception of composites reinforced with organic fibers. In view of the complex and defect-sensitive nature of axial compression strength, it seems reasonable to expect that there also might be size effects in this property. By extension, one could generalize, and raise the issue of inherent size dependence for all PMC strength properties.

The implications of size effects are important and potentially critical for large structures such as bridges and commercial aircraft fuselages. For these applications, the volume of material in the structure may be ten orders of magnitude greater than those of conventional test coupons used to define allowable design strength properties. For a material whose strength is described by a Weibull strength distribution, the ratio of the median strengths of two volumes of material subjected to a uniform tensile strength distribution is given by

$$s_2^*/s_1^* = (V_1/V_2)^{1/m} \quad (1)$$

where s_1^* is the median strength of volume V_1 , s_2^* is the strength of volume V_2 and m is the material Weibull modulus or shape parameter, an inverse measure of strength scatter [1]. Fig. 1 shows how strength varies with volume ratio for several values of m .

To illustrate the significance of size effect, consider a material whose strength coefficient of variation, C , is 5%, which is a typical number for a well made composite. The Weibull modulus, m , for this material is about 24 (m is approximately given by $m = 1.2/C$). Eqn (1) predicts a 50% reduction in strength for an eight-order-of-magnitude volume increase. The decrease in strength for materials displaying greater scatter is even more dramatic. Potential strength decreases of this order of magnitude cannot be prudently ignored.

Assuming the existence of size effects, the question arises as to how they can be accounted for in the development of large structures. In this paper, we examine the evidence for size effects and find it convincing. We then consider current design methodology and failure criteria. Next, we propose simple, design-oriented failure criteria incorporating size effects. Finally, we suggest a research program to expand our understanding of these important issues.

EVIDENCE FOR SIZE EFFECTS

The existence of size effects in composite materials is controversial. Arguments on the subject frequently take on a religious quality, with each person defending her or his own position dogmatically. The intensity of feeling is exceeded only by questions relating to test methods and failure criteria. Considering the criticality of material strength in structural design, it is interesting that the issue of size effects has not received more attention. However, there have been a significant number of works in which the authors report evidence for size effects. One of the problems is that in each case it is often possible to explain the test results in other ways. It is this author's opinion that, taken as a whole, there is convincing evidence for the existence of size effects in PMCs. In this section, we discuss a number of representative works on the subject, expanding the review presented in [2]. The basic issue is well defined by Hitchon and Phillips: would small specimens cut from a large structure have the same strength characteristics (e.g. mean and standard deviation) as the structure itself when subjected to the same state of uniform stress [3]? A critical corollary issue is whether the process used to make test coupons is representative of that employed for the structure. We look at axial tension, axial compression, transverse tension, and axial flexure of unidirectional composites; the influence of hole size and number of holes on the strength of laminates; and a number of other phenomena.

Axial Tensile Strength of Unidirectional Composites

It has been well established that the mean tensile strengths of glass, carbon (graphite), boron and aramid single filaments decrease with increasing length, so that there is little dispute about size effect in key reinforcements [4,5,6,7]. In [4], it was shown that, consistent with statistical bundle theory, the mean tensile strengths of untwisted aramid yarns is less than that of single filaments and also decreases as length increases with a slope similar to that for single filaments. It was also predicted and observed in that reference that the mean tensile strength of twisted fiber bundles decreases with increasing length, but at a lower slope than for untwisted bundles.

It is well established that tensile failure of unidirectional composites results from a complex process associated with a statistical accumulation of fiber breaks, e.g. [8,9]. Bullock found that unidirectional tensile coupons were 18-51% weaker than impregnated strands which have smaller volumes [10]. Hitchon and Phillips found that unidirectional tensile rings were 23% weaker than smaller tensile coupons. Data of G. Dorey, reported in [11], showed a strength reduction of 15 to 20% as specimen volume increased by about three orders of magnitude.

Axial Compressive Strength of Unidirectional Composites

Reeder found that axial compression strength decreased with increasing specimen length [12] and data of Camponeschi [13] showed a decrease with increasing thickness.

Transverse Tensile Strength of Unidirectional Composites

O'Brien and Salpekar report a significant decrease in transverse tensile strength with increasing specimen volume [14]. Here we point out that there is an important distinction between the effects of volume on transverse tensile strength of unidirectional composites and the influence of ply thickness on transverse strength in cross-ply laminates studied in [15]. In the latter case, constraint provided by axial layers may play a key role. No such constraint exists in unidirectional composites.

Flexural Strength of Unidirectional Composites

It has been widely observed for decades that the axial flexural strength of unidirectional composites is generally significantly higher than axial tensile strength, e.g. [10]. This is a property shared with ceramics. However, a significant difference between ceramics and composites is that, whereas the compression strength of ceramics is typically much higher than flexural strength, composite flexural strength often exceeds both compression strength and tensile strength. For example, it has been found that flexural strengths of unidirectional coupons can exceed tensile strengths by as much as 44% and compressive strengths by as much as 56%, e.g. [10,16,17,18]. Wisnom found that the flexural strength of 100-ply unidirectional coupons was 15% weaker than that of 25-ply coupons, and apparent size effects occurred in both tension and compression [19].

Effect of Holes on Laminate Strength

It is widely recognized that the reduction in laminate strength caused by circular holes increases with increasing hole size, e.g. [20]. One explanation is that the volume of material subjected to a stress concentration increases with increasing hole diameter, so that the phenomenon results from

a size effect. Vermeeren found hole size effects in the tensile strengths of GLARE and ARALL laminates, which consist of aramid and glass PMCs, respectively, bonded to aluminum [28]. In that work, the phenomenon was attributed to size effects. Chou and Croman found that the static compression strength of specimens with three holes in series was 11% lower than for a coupon with one hole, and the fatigue life (cycles to failure) 69% lower [21].

Other Evidence for Size Effects

There are numerous other examples of evidence for size effects and statistically based failure processes in PMCs. Here are some examples. Laminate failure is preceded by the statistical accumulation of transverse cracks which initiate at flaws scattered throughout the material [16, 22-24]. Rodini and Eisenmann reported evidence of a possible size effect associated with edge delamination caused by free edge stresses [25]. In an early paper, it was found that the burst strength of filament wound pressure vessels tended to decrease with increasing volume of material, although there were notable exceptions [26]. Other significant papers dealing with size effects are [27, 29 and 30].

DESIGN METHODOLOGY AND FAILURE CRITERIA

In this section, we briefly review current design methodology, failure criteria and statistical size effect models, and propose simple design-oriented failure criteria incorporating size effects.

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

Design methodology is obviously a many-faceted, complex subject. However, we limit our discussion to a key aspect which relates to the issues at hand. A widely observed practice, at least in the U. S. aerospace industry, is to use fiber-dominated laminates to overcome the limitations imposed by the low transverse strengths of PMC materials. In this approach, transverse failures in layers are often ignored. A common manifestation of this philosophy is known as the "10% Rule", which requires that at least 10% of the fibers in a laminate be placed in principal load directions, e.g. [31]. We make use of this approach in our proposed methodology.

MULTIAXIAL STRENGTH CRITERIA

It is inelegant, but accurate, to describe the status of failure criteria for composites subjected to combined stresses as a can of worms. For example, Burk found many criteria in use throughout industry [32]. Virtually all are mathematical expressions unrelated to physical phenomenon, although there have been some attempts to model physical processes, e.g. [33]. An early survey of empirical failure criteria by Sendeckyj [34] turned up 45 references for anisotropic materials. The number has increased significantly in the intervening years.

Failure criteria can be broken down into three main categories, maximum stress, maximum strain and a variety of polynomial interaction criteria. Hart-Smith has proposed a fourth [35,36]. Burk conducted a survey some years ago, and found that about half the respondents used either the maximum strain or maximum stress criteria [32]. The remainder used a variety of interaction criteria. Hart-Smith estimates that at present the design of only about 1% of the aircraft structures in use are governed by unnotched laminate strength. For the rest, joints, damage tolerance and stiffness are the dominant factors [36]. However, we expect that as structural size increases, unnotched laminate strength will become increasingly important.

A major deficiency of most polynomial failure criteria is that they fail to identify a failure mode, as maximum strain and maximum stress do. Further, for very large structures we can anticipate that, based on the work of O'Brien and Salpekar [14], transverse tensile strength will be very low, leading to unrealistically conservative failure predictions when interaction criteria are used. The same is true when transverse failure is considered in maximum stress and maximum strain criteria.

For these reasons, we propose a maximum stress failure criterion in which only axial tension and axial compression are considered. This approach provides a simple way to incorporate size effect, as discussed later.

STATISTICAL SIZE EFFECT MODELS

The statistical methods of analysis used for composite strength can be divided into two main categories. In the first, the material is treated at the macroscopic level as if it were an effectively homogeneous material. The most common macroscopic model for composite strength is that of classical Weibull theory [1]. This approach is applied to composites in [10 and 21].

The second class of analytical methods is based on micromechanical statistical failure models, as in [8, 37-40]. At least some of the micromechanics models for tensile strength of unidirectional composites predict a size effect similar to that based on Weibull theory, e.g. [41]. The micromechanics twisted fiber bundle model of [4], which provides good agreement with experimental data for aramid fibers, also predicts a size effect.

PROPOSED FAILURE CRITERIA INCORPORATING SIZE EFFECTS

We propose failure criteria based on the design methodology described earlier. Namely, we assume that laminates are designed according to the 10% Rule. We ignore transverse failure. We assume that laminate failure occurs when the fibers in any layer exceed their corresponding allowable strength in tension or compression.

The next question is the nature of size effects and how to incorporate them into the design methodology. In the absence of better information, we assume as a starting point that axial tensile strength and compressive strengths can be represented by two-parameter Weibull models. Statistical size effects can be introduced in several ways. Perhaps the simplest is to use Eqn (1) to reduce design strength allowable values determined from tension and compression coupon tests. In this approach, V_1 is the coupon volume and V_2 the volume of the structure. However, this may be too conservative, as the stress distribution typically will not be uniform most structures.

An alternative method is to return to the basic strength theory of Weibull [1]. The probability of failure of a structure subjected to a stress distribution, s is given by

$$P(s) = 1 - \exp\left\{ - \sum_A \sum_{j=1}^N [s(j)/s(t,c)]^{m(t,c)} t(j) dA \right\} \quad (2)$$

where A is the surface area of the structure, $t(j)$ is the thickness of layer j , N is the number of layers in the structure, and $s(j)$ is the axial tensile or compressive stress in layer j . There are two Weibull scale parameters or reference strength levels which are determined from coupon tests, one for tension, $s(t)$, and one for compression, $s(c)$. Similarly, there are two corresponding Weibull shape parameters, $m(t)$ and $m(c)$, which are determined from the same tests. The appropriate values of m and s should be used in Eqn (2), depending on whether the axial stress in the layer is tensile or compressive. In Eqn (2) we have represented the probability of failure as a summation rather than an integral because in current practice it typically would be used in conjunction with a finite element model.

Using this methodology, the design engineer can define an acceptable probability of failure for the particular application. We believe this is a simple, reasonable and prudent initial approach to large structure design, given the current state of knowledge. As we learn more about size effects and multiaxial failure criteria, it undoubtedly will have to be modified.

FUTURE WORK

The two strength issues discussed in this paper, size effects and multiaxial failure criteria, are basic, controversial, and reveal how limited is our understanding of very fundamental aspects of composite behavior. Clearly, there is a need to advance our knowledge in these important areas.

We believe that the most critical need at this time is for careful experiments to quantify the severity of size effects. This will require considerable planning and thorough design and analysis of test specimens to identify areas of possible stress concentrations which could influence test results. Specimen preparation also will require great care to assure that it will be possible to distinguish inherent material variability from process variability. One approach might be to machine coupons from large structures and compare their strength properties with those of coupons made separately. All tests specimens should be thoroughly instrumented to detect possible stress nonuniformities.

It would be desirable to include in the program a variety of fibers including E-glass, boron, aramid and several types of carbon. Resin selection will require some consideration. It might be

desirable to use the same matrix for all composites, as long as its failure strain is large enough so that it is not the limiting factor. Anticipating future micromechanical studies, the tensile strength distribution of single filaments and matrix properties should be carefully defined. A significant quantity of material should be preserved for subsequent tests, as the initial tests undoubtedly will raise as many questions as they answer.

The simplest size effect study, and a good place to start, is undoubtedly axial tensile strength of unidirectional composites. Here, it should not be too difficult to fabricate and test good quality specimens having a range of widths, thicknesses and lengths. The results of this initial program should provide important insight into tensile strength size effects and guidelines for studies of other properties, such as axial compression strength and laminate strength characteristics.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we reviewed what we consider to be a significant body of evidence showing that strength properties of polymer matrix composites decrease with increasing material volume. These size effects raise serious questions about the current practice of using small standard coupons to determine design strength allowables for structures which may have material volumes ten orders of magnitude greater. We proposed a simple design methodology in which fiber-dominated laminates are used, transverse failure is ignored and axial tension and compression strengths are considered to be represented by Weibull strength distributions. Guidelines for additional work are proposed.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

I am grateful to Professors Michael Bader and Keith Kedward for valuable discussions during the preparation of this paper.

REFERENCES

1. W. Weibull, "A Statistical Theory of Strength of Materials", Ing. Vetenskaps. Akad. Handl. NR 151, 1939.
2. C. Zweben, "Is there a size effect in composites?", *Composites*, 25, 6, 1994, pp. 451-454.
3. J. W. Hitchon and D.C. Phillips, "The effect of specimen size on the strength of cfrp", *Composites*, Vol. 9 April, 1978, pp. 119-124.
4. C. Zweben, W. S. Smith and M. W. Wardle, "Test Methods for Fiber Tensile Strength, Composite Flexural Modulus and Properties of Fabric-Reinforced Laminates", Composite Materials: Testing and Design - Fifth Conference, ASTM STP 674, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1979, pp. 228-262.
5. A. G. Metcalfe and G. K. Schmitz, *Proceedings, American Society for Testing and Materials*, Vol. 64, 1964, p. 1075.
6. H. W. Herring, "Selected Mechanical and Physical Properties of Boron Filaments", NASA TN D-3202, National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Langley, Virginia, 1966.
7. R. J. Diefendorf and E. Tokarsky, *Polymer Engineering and Science*, Vol. 15, No. 3, 1975, pp. 150-159.
8. B. W. Rosen, "Mechanics of Fiber Strengthening", Fiber Composite Materials, American Society for Metals, Metals Park, Ohio, 1965.
9. P. W. Manders and M. G. Bader, "The strength of hybrid glass/carbon fibre composites, Part 2 A statistical model", *J. of Materials Science*, Vol. 16, 1981, pp. 2246-2256.
10. R. E. Bullock, "Strength Ratios of Composite Materials in Flexure and in Tension", *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 8, 1974, pp. 200-206.
11. S.B. Batdorf., "Note on Composite Size Effects", *Journal of Composites Technology & Research*, 11, 1, 1989, pp. 35-37.
12. J.R. Reeder, "Comparison of the Compressive Strength for Stitched and Toughened Composite Systems, NASA Technical Memorandum 10918, April 1994.
13. E.T. Camponeschi, Jr., "Compression Testing of Thick-Section Composite Materials", Report DTRC-SME-89/73, David Taylor Research Center, Bethesda, Maryland, October 1989.

14. T.K. O'Brien and S.A. Salpekar, "Scale Effects on the Transverse Tensile Strength of Graphite/Epoxy Composites", ASTM STP-1206, Composite Materials: Testing and Design, Volume 11, E. Camponeschi, ed. American Society for Testing and Materials, 1995, pp. 23-52.
15. A. Parvizi, et al., "Constrained cracking in glass fibre-reinforced epoxy cross-ply laminates", J. Materials Science, Vol. 13, 1978, pp. 195-201.
16. B. E. Kaminski, "Effects of Specimen Geometry on the Strength of Composite Materials", Analysis of the Test Methods for High Modulus Fibers and Composites, ASTM STP 521, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1973.
17. C. Zweben, "The Flexural Strength of Aramid Fiber Composites", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 12, 1978, pp. 422-430.
18. K. R. Berg and J. Ramsey, "Metal Aircraft Structural Elements Reinforced with Graphite Filamentary Composites", NASA CR - 112162, August 1972.
19. M. R. Wisnom, "the Effect of Specimen Size on the Bending Strength of Unidirectional Carbon Fibre-Epoxy", Composite Structures, Vol. 18, 1991, pp. 47-63.
20. M. E. Waddoups, J. R. Eisenmann and B. E. Kaminski, "Macroscopic Fracture Mechanics of Advanced Composite Materials", J. Composite Materials, Vol. 5, October 1971, pp. 446-454.
21. P. C. Chou and R. Croman, "Scale Effect in Fatigue of Composite Materials", J. Composite Materials, Vol. 13, July 1979, pp. 178-194.
22. Wang, A. S. D., Fracture mechanics of sublaminar cracks in composite materials", Composites Technology Review, Vol. 6, No. 2, Summer 1984, pp. 45-62.
23. Highsmith, A. L. and Reifsnider, K. L., "Stiffness-Reduction Mechanisms in Composite Laminates", Damage in Composite Materials, ASTM STP 775, K. L. Reifsnider, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, 1982, pp. 103-117.
24. G. J. Dvorak and N. Laws, "Analysis of First Ply Failure in Composite Laminates", Engineering Fracture Mechanics, Vol. 25, Nos. 5/6, pp. 763-770, 1986.
25. B. T. Rodini and J. R. Eisenmann, "An analytical and experimental investigation of edge delamination in composite laminates", Fibrous Composites in Structural Design, Plenum Press, New York, 1980, pp. 441-458.
26. L. A. Riedinger, M. H. Kural, and G. W. Reed, Jr., "Evaluation of the Potential Structural Performance of Composites", Mechanics of Composite Materials, F. W. Wendt, H. Liebowitz, and N. Perrone, Editors, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1970, pp. 481-525.
27. Jackson, K.E., Kellas, S., and Morton, J., Scale Effects in the Response and Failure of Fiber Reinforced Composite Laminates Loaded in Tension and in Flexure", Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 26, No. 18, 1992, pp. 2674-2705.
28. C.A.J.R. Vermeeren, "The blunt notch behaviour of Metal Laminates: ARALL and GLARE", Delft University of Technology, Report LR-617, January 1990.
29. Jackson, K.E., "Scaling Effects in the Flexural Response and Failure of Composite Beams", AIAA Journal, Vol. 30, No. 8, August 1992, pp. 2099-2105.
30. Kellas, S. and Morton, J., "Strength Scaling in Fiber Composites", NASA Contractor Report 4335, November 1990.
31. Grimes, G. C. "Tape composite material allowables application in airframe design/analysis", Composite Engineering, Vol. 3, Nos. 7-8, 1993, pp. 777-804.
32. Burk, R. C. "Standard failure criteria needed for advanced composites", Aeronautics and Astronautics, June 1983, pp. 58-62.
33. C. Zweben, "Failure Analysis of Unidirectional Fiber Composites under Combined Axial Tension and Shear", J. Mech. Phys. Solids, 22, 1974, pp. 193-215.
34. G.P. Sendekyj, "A Brief Survey of Empirical Multiaxial Strength Criteria for Composites", Composite Materials: Testing and Design (Second Conference), ASTM STP 497, American Society for Testing and Materials, 1972, pp. 41-51.
35. A. Kelly, "Multiaxial Stress Failure", Concise Encyclopedia of Composite Materials, Revised Edition, A. Kelly, ed., Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1994.
36. L.J. Hart-Smith, "The role of biaxial stresses in discriminating between meaningful and illusory composite failure theories", Composite Structures, 25, 1993, pp. 3-20.
37. C. Zweben, "A Bounding Approach to the Strength of Composite Materials", Engineering Fracture Mechanics, Vol. 4, 1972, pp. 1-8.
38. S. L. Phoenix, "Probabilistic Concepts in Modeling the Tensile Strength Behavior of Fiber Bundles and Unidirectional Fiber Matrix Composites", Composite Materials: Testing and

Design, ASTM STP 546, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1974, pp. 130-151.

39. D. G. Harlow, "Properties of the Strength Distribution for Composite Materials", Composite Materials: Testing and Design - Fifth Conference, ASTM STP 674, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia, 1979.
40. C. Zweben, "Tensile Strength of Hybrid Composites", *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 12, No. 7, 1977, pp. 1325-1337.
41. C. Zweben, "The Effect of Stress Nonuniformity and Size on the Strength of Composite Materials", *Composites Technology Review*, Vol. 3, No. 1, 1981, pp. 23-26.

Figure 1. Variation of strength ratio with volume ratio predicted by Weibull strength theory [1].